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3 **Modeling of small molecule's affinity to phospholipids using IAM-HPLC and QSRR**
4 **approach enhanced by similarity-based machine algorithms**

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15 **Abstract:**

16 Immobilized artificial membrane chromatography (IAM) has been proposed as a more
17 biosimilar alternative to classical lipophilicity measurement. Determination of small molecule's
18 affinity to phospholipids can be supported for predicting their behavior in the human body.
19 Therefore, a better understanding of the molecular interaction mechanism between small
20 xenobiotics and phospholipids can accelerate drug discovery. Here, the quantitative structure-
21 retention relationships (QSRR) approach was integrated with mechanistic descriptors
22 calculated using Chemicalize software to propose an easy-to-interpretation QSRR model.
23 Considering the heterogeneous character of the data set, locally weighted least squares kernel
24 regression belonging to similarity-based machine learning methods have been applied. The
25 results showed that lipophilicity, charge, and maximum projection area determine molecule
26 binding to phospholipids. Full validation of the obtained model based on OECD
27 recommendations has been performed and the applicability domain was defined using the
28 probability-oriented distance-based approach. The high values of predictive squared correlation
29 coefficient (Q^2), and small root mean square error of prediction (RMSEP), 0.812 and 6.739,
30 respectively, confirmed that the obtained QSRR model is not well-fitted to the training data but
31 also showed prediction power. Additionally, only 1.5% of molecules from the training set and
32 2.8% from the validation test are outside the applicability domain, confirming great predictive
33 abilities.

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35 **Key words:** Immobilized artificial membrane chromatography; quantitative structure-
36 retention relationships; similarity-based machine learning; QSRR

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38 **List of abbreviations**

39

40 IAM - immobilized artificial membrane

41 QSRR - quantitative structure-property relationships

42 ML - machine learning

43 SBM - similarity-based machine learning methods

44 CHI_{IAM} - chromatographic hydrophobicity index with an immobilized artificial membrane

45 MLR - multiple linear regression

46 GA - genetic algorithm

47 KwLPR - locally weighted least squares kernel regression

48 PCA - principal component analysis

49 t-SNE - t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding

50 R^2 - coefficient of determination

51 Q^2_{loo} - correlation coefficient of leave-one-out cross-validation

52 $RMSE_{loo}$ - root-mean-square error of leave-one-out cross-validation

53 $RMSE_C$ - root mean square error of calibration

54 $RMSE_P$ - root mean square error of prediction

55 Q^2 - predictive squared correlation coefficient

56 CCC - concordance correlation coefficient

57

58 **1. Introduction**

59 Discovering and developing new drugs is an expensive, demanding, and time-
60 consuming process with uncertain outcomes in clinical trials[1]. Nowadays, chemical synthesis
61 and biological screening possibilities in the drug discovery pipeline have significantly
62 increased. However, poor pharmacokinetic properties and high toxicity have been considered
63 major limitations of drug candidates. Therefore, lipophilicity assessment is an essential process
64 in drug discovery since it noticeably affects the diffusion of molecules through a biological
65 membrane[2], determining the molecule's pharmacokinetic properties and toxicity[3]. The
66 detailed experimental protocols proposed by OECD (test no 107 and 117) and several
67 procedures developed for academic and industrial institutions describe methods for lipophilicity
68 assessment based on the shake flask method or reversed-phase liquid chromatography (RP-
69 LC)[4–10]. Nevertheless, currently, more biosimilar alternatives to classical lipophilicity are
70 available. One of the alternatives is immobilized artificial membrane (IAM) chromatography.
71 The IAM stationary phase shows superior biomimetic properties compared to classical
72 lipophilicity measurement since phosphatidylcholine molecules (the primary phospholipid of
73 cell membranes) are covalently bound to silica, mimicking the phospholipid membrane
74 monolayer[11].

75 The first HPLC columns with an immobilized artificial membrane were developed by
76 Pidgeon et al. in 1989[12]. IAM high-performance liquid chromatography (IAM-HPLC) allows
77 for assessing the affinity to phospholipids while maintaining all the advantages of HPLC. It is
78 worth emphasizing that chromatographic approaches hold great promise for high-throughput
79 screening among non-cell-based methods. Modern HPLC systems are highly automated and
80 very popular in academia and the pharmaceutical industry. [13].

81 The relationship between retention and the chemical structure of analytes has attracted
82 attention from the beginning of chromatographic research. Kaliszan initiated and introduced a

83 particular type of quantitative structure-property relationships (QSPR) analysis, namely the
84 quantitative structure-retention relationships (QSRR), in 1987[14]. Since then, QSRR has been
85 a powerful tool in chromatographic research and has also been applied to study the retention
86 mechanism of IAM-HPLC[15–21].

87 In the past decades, machine learning (ML) and data sciences have made remarkable
88 progress and are being applied in every scientific discipline, including QSPR/QSRR. Among
89 available algorithms, similarity-based machine learning methods (SBM) showed significant
90 advantages in dealing with heterogeneous noisy toxicological data[22,23]. Nonetheless, the use
91 of SBM in the case of chromatographic data is still in its infancy, although some studies showed
92 its high potential[24].

93 This study's purpose was to understand better the molecular mechanism of interaction
94 between small xenobiotics and phospholipids. IAM-HPLC data was integrated with molecular
95 descriptors via the QSRR approach to realize this goal. A chromatographic hydrophobicity
96 index with an immobilized artificial membrane (CHI_{IAM}) was used as an endpoint in QSRR
97 modeling. Based on a heterogeneous set of 402 molecules, primarily of pharmaceutical or
98 toxicological significance, the QSRR model was developed. The proposed model was validated
99 using retention factors of potential drug candidates, 106 molecules belonging to 5 different
100 chemical classes, analyzed in our laboratory. Using Chemicalize software, mechanistic
101 molecular descriptors were calculated; therefore, the straightforward interpretation of obtained
102 QSRR models can be described. Initial descriptor selection was performed by applying multiple
103 linear regression (MLR) coupled with a genetic algorithm (GA). Additionally, inspired by
104 recent developments of SBM, especially locally weighted least squares kernel regression
105 (KwLPR), we checked that KwLPR can increase model performances.

106 **2. Materials and methods**

107 **2.1 Data collection**

108 In this study, we collected data expressing molecules' affinity to phospholipids determined
109 based on fast gradient methods established by Valko and co-workers[25]. The experimental
110 protocol is based on fast acetonitrile gradient elution; in such conditions, the CHI_{IAM} refers to
111 the acetonitrile concentration necessary for the elution of analytes from IAM columns and
112 consequently expresses the binding to phospholipids. CHI_{IAM} values were collected from
113 literature for molecules included in the training set[26–30] and for drug candidates used as the
114 validation set[31–35]. Drug candidates represented five chemical classes; isoxazoles,
115 fluoroquinolones, arylpiperazines, sulfonamides and oleanolic acid derivatives.

116 Although Regis Technologies Inc. (Morton Grove, IL, USA) is the only manufacturer of the
117 IAM stationary phase, some changes in the column manufacturing process occurred. Since
118 "type A" silica was no longer available, the IAM column introduced "type B" silica in 2018,
119 causing slight changes to the surface and properties of the silica beds. Considering reports
120 published by Valko and co-workers [36], we decided to combine data coming from "new" and
121 "old" IAM columns since they proved that, in general, the CHI_{IAM} values from the "new" IAM
122 column were comparable with the values obtained from the previous batches of IAM columns
123 and differences occurred only for small polar basic compounds. Therefore, to maximize the size
124 of the training set, we decided not to limit data only to one type of IAM column. In most studies,
125 ammonium acetate was used as water-mobile phases; in two research, the phosphate buffer was
126 applied[34,35], but in both cases, pH was 7.4 to mimic physiological conditions. A high
127 correlation between CHI_{IAM} of reference substances and the fact that investigated isoxazoles
128 and oleanolic acid derivatives are mostly presented as the neutral forms under applied
129 conditions indicated that the data are comparable.

130 Molecular weight has been used as a criterion for including or excluding molecules. Since the
131 developing model will be dedicated to low-molecular substances, the cutoff was set at 650

132 g/mol level. Following the FAIRness recommendation on how to share the (meta)data[37], all
133 data collected during this study (CHI_{IAM}) and calculated (molecular descriptors) together with
134 molecular identification (SMILES notation) are available as supplementary materials and in the
135 author's GitHub as machine-readable form making it interoperability.

136 **2.2 Calculation of molecular descriptors**

137 For the calculation of molecular descriptors, Chemicalize software (<https://chemicalize.com/>)
138 was applied. The basic version of subscriptions is free of cost and allows for the calculation of
139 molecular properties of up to 12 non-hydrogen atoms molecules. During this study, several
140 classes of theoretical descriptors were calculated, referring to molecules' geometrical,
141 topological, and bulkiness-related properties. Also, descriptors were obtained to code the
142 molecule's lipophilicity, including $\log P$ and $\log D_{7.4}$, charge, and ability to form H-bonds. All
143 calculated descriptors were collected in supplementary materials together with 2D molecule
144 structures and information about chemical character established based on the most dominant
145 form in experimental pH (7.4).

146 **2.3 Data analysis**

147 Principal component analysis (PCA) and t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE)
148 were performed to explore similarities and dissimilarities of observed structures. PCA and
149 t-SNE were calculated for databases of calculated descriptors. Before analysis, data were
150 standardized to eliminate the impact of different scales by using the Z-score scaling algorithm
151 ($V = \text{mean of } V/\delta$, where V is the value of variables and δ is the standard deviation). In the
152 case of t-SNE, perplexity was 5, whereas the maximum number of interactions was 1000. Both
153 analyses were performed in the *R* environment.

154 **2.4 QSRR modeling**

155 The first step of QSRR modeling includes multiple linear regression algorithms supported by
156 GA. For the calculation of GA-MLR, QSARINS software was used[38]. The set of parameters
157 applied to control GA was the size of the population—200 and the mutation rate—20%. Priori
158 to analyze data were divided into two groups, the training group ($n = 408, \approx 80\%$) and the
159 testing group ($n = 106, \approx 20\%$) included 5 following chemical classes of drug candidates:
160 oleanolic acid derivatives, sulfonamide derivatives, arylpiperazine derivatives, isoxazolo
161 derivatives, and fluoroquinolone derivatives. Next, based on the selected descriptors, KwLPR
162 was calculated using the protocol proposed by Gajewicz-Skrętna and all [23].

163 The model fitting, robustness, and predictive abilities were assessed by using the
164 following statistical figures: coefficient of determination (R^2), correlation coefficient of leave-
165 one-out cross-validation (Q^2_{loo}), root-mean-square error of leave-one-out cross-validation
166 ($RMSE_{loo}$), root mean square error of calibration ($RMSE_C$), root mean square error of prediction
167 ($RMSE_P$), predictive squared correlation coefficient (Q^2), and concordance correlation
168 coefficient (CCC). Detailed descriptions and formulas of all investigated statistical parameters
169 are described in supplementary material.

170 For the final model the applicability domain was defined using the probability-oriented
171 distance-based approach proposed by Gajewicz-Skrętna[39]. Data analysis and results
172 visualization have been performed using RStudio software (R version 4.1.1) with “carat” and
173 “ggplot2” packages[40].

174 **3. Results and discussion**

175 **3.1 Data distribution in datasets**

176

177 In this study, the data set of 508 molecules, mostly with therapeutic or toxicological potency,
178 has been collected from studies published by Valko[26–29] and for our *in-house* data from
179 previously published research[30–33,35]. Since some molecules were analyzed in both

180 laboratories, we checked differences in the CHI_{IAM} indices (Figure S1). Generally, the CHI_{IAM}
181 values did not vary by more than five units[41], which can be considered a typical method
182 deviation; only for seven molecules, this difference was slightly large but still less than seven
183 units. Based on these results, it can be concluded that Valko's protocol demonstrates high
184 reproducibility.

185 Then using Chemicalize software, the ionization state of molecules under experimental
186 conditions was determined (Figure 1A). Most molecules are present predominantly in neutral
187 form (46%), while the numbers of cations and anions are at similar levels, 26% and 19%,
188 respectively. The smallest group (9%) included zwitterions. The distribution of CHI_{IAM} among
189 chemical classes is presented in Figure 1B. Usually, we observed normal distribution in each
190 group, with the p -value of the Shapiro-Wilk test > 0.05 , except for cations where compounds
191 with high CHI_{IAM} values are in the majority.

192 Figure 1. A) Distribution of chemical classes. B) Distribution of CHI_{IAM} among chemical
193 classes

194 After calculating theoretical descriptors, PCA and t-SNE analysis was performed to verify the
195 data structure and remove potential outliers, which can negatively affect the performance of the
196 regression model. PCA is a linear technique that reorients the data into a new coordinate system
197 by identifying the principal components. These principal components are linear combinations
198 of the original features. On the other hand, t-SNE is a non-linear technique that concentrates on
199 preserving pairwise similarities between data points in the high-dimensional space and then
200 represents them in a lower-dimensional space, usually 2D. Both methods allow for the
201 assessment of the similarities or dissimilarities of data points, in the case of this study
202 similarities between drug candidates and model substances were investigated. As can be
203 observed in Figure 2, most drug candidates are mixed with model substances. Only a few
204 oleanolic acid derivatives are outside the circle indicating the 0.95 level of group membership.

205 A similar result was achieved after applying tSNE algorithms, which indicated that no structural
206 outliers are presented in the dataset.

207 Figure 2. Results of exploratory analysis

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209 The criterion of including molecules certainly influenced the obtained results and allowed us to
210 bring a homogeneous data set. While the developing model will be dedicated to a low-molecular
211 substance, the molecular weight for molecules incorporated into train or validation sets was less
212 than 650 g/mol. This limitation is based Muegge filter indicates that drug candidates should
213 weigh less than 600 g/mol. We used this filter since it is the most liberal among other drug-
214 likeness-tools, where typically the cut-off criterion is 500 g/mol and added circa 10% of the
215 maximum weight to not limit the use of the obtained model for molecules that only small exceed
216 the critical weight.

217 **3.2 QSRR modeling**

218 There are different methods to measure the retention of analytes in IAM-HPLC, depending on
219 the elution technique used. Two of the most commonly employed methods include extrapolated
220 $\log k_{wIAM}$ parameters, which measure retention in the pure water phase and are calculated based
221 on several isocratic elution and CHI_{IAM} determined in gradient elution corresponding to equal
222 distribution between stationary and mobile phase. Upon analyzing previously published QSRR
223 models for IAM chromatography, collected in Table 1, it seems that the interaction between the
224 molecule and IAM stationary phase is primarily driven by lipophilicity. Practically each
225 obtained model presents lipophilicity-related descriptors. Nevertheless, it should be highlighted
226 that the retention is not only governed by lipophilicity since, in each model, additional
227 descriptors occur. Descriptors related to a molecule's charge, ability to form H-bonds, or
228 geometry also occurred relatively often. Considering the above facts, we decided to employ

229 Chemicalize for descriptor calculation because this software covers the most frequently used
230 descriptor classes for modeling IAM retention. Additionally, as an online software,
231 Chemicalize provides rapid calculations and does not require highly efficient hardware
232 compared to density functional theory (DFT) calculations, which give more precision
233 calculations. Still, due to their complexity, their use in predictive models is very limited.
234 Moreover, Chemicalize does not require extensive knowledge of computational chemistry,
235 which is necessary to perform DFT calculations.

236 **3.2.1 MLR modeling**

237 The first step of our investigation concerned checking linear modeling. GA supports the
238 selection of molecular descriptors that determine a molecule's affinity to phospholipids.
239 Shortly, in the case of GA-MLR the population of variables is initially created randomly. The
240 next step calculates the model performance and survives the model with the highest metrics.
241 Loop for further crossover and mutation specified the properties of the algorithm. The best
242 obtained GA-MLR model is presented below, whereas statistical figures are given in Table 2.

$$243 \quad \text{CHI}_{\text{IAM}} = 3.56(\pm 3.19) + 5.84(\pm 0.48) \log P + 11.08(\pm 1.35) q + 0.14(\pm 0.04) \text{MPA}$$

244 Among investigated descriptors, lipophilicity ($\log P$), molecule charge (q), and maximum
245 projection area (MPA) determine CHI_{IAM} . As might be expected, lipophilicity ($\log P$) is highly
246 affected by affinity to phospholipids, and more lipophilic structures show higher affinity to
247 phospholipids. However, interactions with phospholipids are more complex than only the effect
248 of the molecule's lipophilicity, which can explain the chemical nature of phosphatidylcholine.
249 At a pH of 7.4, the IAM stationary phase surface has a zwitterionic character and can interact
250 with negatively and positively charged molecules. Avdeef and his colleagues' theory suggests
251 that the choline moieties with a positive charge at pH 7.4 are located in the outer part of the
252 IAM layer [42]. On the other hand, the phosphate groups have a negative charge at the same

253 pH and are present in the inner part of the IAM surface [15,16]. Vrakas et al. showed that
254 electrostatic interactions with phospholipid-charged centers are an important factor governing
255 retention in IAM[43]. Therefore, the presence of molecule charge (q) in the obtained QSRR
256 model can explain this type of interaction driven mostly by electronic force. Molecule charge
257 is calculated by Chemically based on the partial charge distribution of the molecule, which is
258 determined by the electronegativity of the atoms within the molecule. Another descriptor
259 included in the obtained model is MPA, which refers to the maximum projection areas of the
260 conformer based on the van der Waals radius. This molecular descriptor also has a significant
261 physicochemical sense; molecules with higher MPA have a higher area for hydrophobic
262 interaction with phosphatidylcholine majority.

263 **3.2.2 KwLPR**

264 The next step of our investigation focuses on applying SBM algorithms, which is considered
265 a rational choice for analysis of heterogeneous datasets. To drive the regression model
266 coefficients, SMB methods use only a small collection of training data from the local
267 neighborhood chemically similar to a given target point instead of the entire training set that
268 spans a wide variety of chemicals[23].

269 Recently, KwLPR has demonstrated its superiority in modeling toxicological data[23].
270 Briefly, the KwLPR algorithm uses a sliding smoothing window to estimate data. At each query
271 point, a polynomial of degree 0 or 1 is fit locally using specific bandwidth and kernel functions.
272 During calculation three various kernel functions have been tested: gaussian, epanechnikov,
273 and uniform. This helps to reduce the mean squared error of the individual models and
274 chemicals. A detailed description of KwLPR can be found in the work published by Gajewicz-
275 Skretna and co-workers where they demonstrated the use of the KwLPR algorithm for
276 QSAR/QSPR/QSTR modeling[23]. Analyzing statistical figures of obtained MLR and KwLPR
277 models, also significant improvement is visible in each parameter. What is especially important

278 is that the RMSE for the training and validation sets are very small, 6.435 and 6.739,
279 respectively, so they are very close to typical analytical errors for this method which is 5 CHI_{IAM}
280 units. Overall, the high values of R^2 , Q^2 , Q^2_{loo} , and small $RMSE_C$ and $RMSE_P$ confirmed that
281 the obtained KwLPR model is not well-fitted to the training data but also showed prediction
282 power. This is clearly visible by looking at the fit of the predicted values to the observed ones,
283 presented in Figure 3A.

284 Figure 3) Results of KwLPR regression; A) Observed CHI_{IAM} vs. predicted by model; B)
285 $RMSE_P$ for tested groups of drug candidates; C) applicability domain defined using the
286 probability-oriented distance-based approach.

287 Analyzed each group of drug candidates separately, we can clearly see that $RMSE_P$ for four
288 among five tested groups is close to 5 (Figure 3B). Comparing statistics for previously
289 published local models calculated for arylpiperazine, sulfonamide, and oleanolic acid
290 derivatives, although the statistics from local models are better, the values predicted by KwLPR
291 are merely slightly worse. Only in the case of isoxazole derivatives the significantly higher
292 $RMSE_P$ has been noticed than in the case of the local QSRR model (10.04 vs. 1.98). If we look
293 for raw data, we see that chemicalized treat isoxazoles as charged molecules, whereas based on
294 DFT experiments, we know that isoxazoles are non-ionized under experimental conditions.
295 Probably, this was the main reason why, in this class of chemicals, we received significantly
296 worse predictions. Another possible factor that may have contributed to the better prediction
297 accuracy of the local models is that the pool of molecular descriptors used was significantly
298 higher than in this study. In this study, the molecular descriptors were limited to those that
299 allowed for mechanistic interpretation. What is equally important, in the case of local models,
300 the training set was based on structurally similar drug candidates, which resulted in a
301 completely different nature of the study.

302 Therefore, the model presented in this work, which has the character of a global model,
303 should be comparable with other models based on a chemically diverse structure. Nevertheless,

304 the straightforward comparison with most of the previously published QSRR models is
305 impossible since most of them are based on $\log k_w^{\text{IAM}}$ or external validation was not performed.
306 We can compare the obtained data with our previous publication [30], where ANN was applied
307 to predict CHI_{IAM} . A significant improvement has been achieved, especially for CCC and
308 RMSE_p .

309 Since previously published models of IAM-HPLC do not meet OECD principles for
310 validating QSRR models, significant attention has been given to properly validating the
311 obtained KwLPR model. According to OECD recommendations QSRR model must have: *i*) a
312 defined endpoint; *ii*) an unambiguous algorithm; *iii*) a defined domain of applicability; *iv*)
313 appropriate measures of goodness-of-fit, robustness, and predictivity; *v*) a mechanistic
314 interpretation.

315 Considering that the final model is based on the KwLPR, the applicability domain was
316 defined using the probability-oriented distance-based approach proposed by Gajewicz-
317 Skretna[39]. In a nutshell, the probability-oriented distance-based method for determining the
318 model's applicability domain involves four main steps. In the first step, calculating the average
319 Euclidean distance between each training compound and the remaining training set compounds,
320 as well as between each validation compound and all training chemicals used for model
321 development, is required. Then, we need to identify the prediction errors which are commonly
322 known as standardized residuals. To ensure reliable predictions in both the structural domain
323 (model descriptors) and response domain (prediction errors in modeled response), we need to
324 estimate the confidence region. This is done by calculating the boundaries of the 95% and 99%
325 confidence intervals using the Student's t-distribution. This space allows us to evaluate whether
326 a compound falls within the applicability domain and to determine the level of uncertainty
327 associated with it. Only 1.5% molecules from the training set and 2.8% molecules from the

328 validation test are outside the applicability domain (Figure 3C) which also confirmed great
329 predictive abilities.

330 **4. Conclusion**

331 Considering that IAM-HPLC has been applied to the prediction of complex biological
332 properties mostly related to behavior and transport of xenobiotics into the human body, such as
333 the blood-brain barrier permeability (BBB) [44,45], intestinal absorption (HIA)[46], the volume
334 of distribution[47], skin permeation[48,49], and cardiotoxicity[50] both prediction and an
335 understanding of phospholipid binding is important in drug discovery pipeline. Using
336 chemoinformatic tools, we can better understand the intricate interrelationships between
337 chemical structures, physical and chemical properties, and affinity to biological endpoints. The
338 obtained results indicated that lipophilicity, molecules' charge, and their maximum projection
339 area determined molecules binding to phospholipids.

340 Comparing statical figures of the obtained KwLPR model with previously established
341 models, we see better prediction power. Moreover, the KwLPR model has a significantly higher
342 applicability domain than previously published since the investigated data sets were a few times
343 higher. What is more, in the case of the proposed model, the full validation according to the
344 OECD recommendation has been performed.

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350 **References:**

- 352 [1] Danishuddin, V. Kumar, M. Faheem, K.W. Lee, A decade of machine learning-based
353 predictive models for human pharmacokinetics: advances and challenges, *Drug Discov*
354 *Today*. 27 (2021) 529–537. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drudis.2021.09.013>.
- 355 [2] H. van de Waterbeemd, E. Gifford, ADMET in silico modelling: towards prediction
356 paradise?, *Nat Rev Drug Discov*. 2 (2003) 192–204. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd1032>.
- 357 [3] T. Hou, J. Wang, Structure – ADME relationship: still a long way to go?, *Expert Opin*
358 *Drug Met*. 4 (2008) 759–770. <https://doi.org/10.1517/17425255.4.6.759>.
- 359 [4] K. Ciura, J. Nowakowska, P. Pikul, W. Struck-Lewicka, M.J. Markuszewski, A
360 Comparative Quantitative Structure-Retention Relationships Study for Lipophilicity
361 Determination of Compounds with a Phenanthrene Skeleton on Cyano-, Reversed Phase-, and
362 Normal Phase-Thin Layer Chromatography Stationary Phases, *J Aoac Int*. 98 (2015) 345–
363 353. <https://doi.org/10.5740/jaoacint.14-187>.
- 364 [5] K. Ciura, M. Belka, P. Kawczak, T. Bączek, J. Nowakowska, The comparative study of
365 micellar TLC and RP-TLC as potential tools for lipophilicity assessment based on QSRR
366 approach, *J Pharmaceut Biomed*. 149 (2018) 70–79.
367 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2017.10.034>.
- 368 [6] K. Ciura, P. Kawczak, K.E. Greber, H. Kapica, J. Nowakowska, T. Bączek, Application of
369 reversed-phase thin layer chromatography and QSRR modelling for prediction of protein
370 binding of selected β -blockers, *J Pharmaceut Biomed*. 176 (2019) 112767.
371 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2019.07.015>.
- 372 [7] M.-L. Jeličić, D.A. Klarić, J. Kovačić, D. Verbanac, A. Mornar, Accessing Lipophilicity
373 and Biomimetic Chromatography Profile of Biologically Active Ingredients of Botanicals
374 Used in the Treatment of Inflammatory Bowel Disease, *Pharm*. 15 (2022) 965.
375 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph15080965>.
- 376 [8] M. Dąbrowska, M. Starek, G. Chłoń-Rzepa, A. Zagórska, Ł. Komsta, A. Jankowska, M.
377 Ślusarczyk, M. Pawłowski, Estimation of the lipophilicity of purine-2,6-dione-based TRPA1
378 antagonists and PDE4/7 inhibitors with analgesic activity, *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*. 49 (2021)
379 128318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmcl.2021.128318>.
- 380 [9] A. Fernández-Pumarega, S. Amézqueta, E. Fuguet, M. Rosés, Tadpole toxicity prediction
381 using chromatographic systems, *J Chromatogr A*. 1418 (2015) 167–176.
382 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2015.09.056>.
- 383 [10] C. Stergiopoulos, F. Tsopeles, K. Valko, M. Ochsenkühn-Petropoulou, The use of
384 biomimetic chromatography to predict acute aquatic toxicity of pharmaceutical compounds,
385 *Toxicol Environ Chem*. 104 (2022) 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02772248.2021.2005065>.
- 386 [11] A.W. Sobańska, Affinity of Compounds for Phosphatidylcholine-Based Immobilized
387 Artificial Membrane—A Measure of Their Bioconcentration in Aquatic Organisms, *Membr*.
388 12 (2022) 1130. <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes12111130>.

- 389 [12] C. Pidgeon, U.V. Venkataram, Immobilized artificial membrane chromatography:
390 Supports composed of membrane lipids, *Analytical Biochemistry*. 176 (1989) 36–47.
391 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2697\(89\)90269-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2697(89)90269-8).
- 392 [13] K.L. Valko, Biomimetic chromatography—A novel application of the chromatographic
393 principles, *Anal Sci Adv.* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ansa.202200004>.
- 394 [14] R. Kaliszan, QSRR: Quantitative Structure-(Chromatographic) Retention Relationships,
395 *Chem Rev.* 107 (2007) 3212–3246. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr068412z>.
- 396 [15] L. Grumetto, C. Carpentiero, P.D. Vaio, F. Frecentese, F. Barbato, Lipophilic and polar
397 interaction forces between acidic drugs and membrane phospholipids encoded in IAM-HPLC
398 indexes: Their role in membrane partition and relationships with BBB permeation data, *J.*
399 *Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 75 (2013) 165–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2012.11.034>.
- 400 [16] L. Grumetto, C. Carpentiero, F. Barbato, Lipophilic and electrostatic forces encoded in
401 IAM-HPLC indexes of basic drugs: Their role in membrane partition and their relationships
402 with BBB passage data, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 45 (2012) 685–692.
403 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2012.01.008>.
- 404 [17] J. Li, J. Sun, S. Cui, Z. He, Quantitative structure-retention relationship studies using
405 immobilized artificial membrane chromatography I: Amended linear solvation energy
406 relationships with the introduction of a molecular electronic factor, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 1132
407 (2006) 174–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2006.07.073>.
- 408 [18] J. Li, J. Sun, Z. He, Quantitative structure–retention relationship studies with
409 immobilized artificial membrane chromatography: II: Partial least squares regression, *Journal*
410 *of Chromatography A.* 1140 (2007) 174–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2006.11.091>.
- 411 [19] H. Du, J. Watzl, J. Wang, X. Zhang, X. Yao, Z. Hu, Prediction of retention indices of
412 drugs based on immobilized artificial membrane chromatography using Projection Pursuit
413 Regression and Local Lazy Regression, *J. Sep. Sci.* 31 (2008) 2325–2333.
414 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.200700665>.
- 415 [20] E. Dagher-Wojtkowiak, S. Studzińska, B. Buszewski, R. Kaliszan, M.J. Markuszewski,
416 Quantitative structure–retention relationships of ionic liquid cations in characterization of
417 stationary phases for HPLC, *Anal. Methods.* 6 (2013) 1189–1196.
418 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3ay41805g>.
- 419 [21] G. Russo, L. Grumetto, F. Barbato, G. Vistoli, A. Pedretti, Prediction and mechanism
420 elucidation of analyte retention on phospholipid stationary phases (IAM-HPLC) by in silico
421 calculated physico-chemical descriptors, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 99 (2017) 173–184.
422 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2016.11.026>.
- 423 [22] A. Gajewicz-Skretna, E. Wyrzykowska, M. Gromelski, Quantitative multi-species
424 toxicity modeling: Does a multi-species, machine learning model provide better performance
425 than a single-species model for the evaluation of acute aquatic toxicity by organic pollutants?,
426 *Science of The Total Environment.* 861 (2023) 160590.
427 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.160590>.

- 428 [23] A. Gajewicz-Skretna, S. Kar, M. Piotrowska, J. Leszczynski, The kernel-weighted local
429 polynomial regression (KwLPR) approach: an efficient, novel tool for development of
430 QSAR/QSAAR toxicity extrapolation models, 13 (2021) 9. [https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-021-00484-5)
431 [021-00484-5](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-021-00484-5).
- 432 [24] J.P.M. Andries, M. Goodarzi, Y.V. Heyden, Improvement of quantitative structure–
433 retention relationship models for chromatographic retention prediction of peptides applying
434 individual local partial least squares models, *Talanta*. 219 (2020) 121266.
435 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2020.121266>.
- 436 [25] K.L. Valkó, Lipophilicity and biomimetic properties measured by HPLC to support drug
437 discovery, *J Pharmaceut Biomed*. 130 (2016) 35–54.
438 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2016.04.009>.
- 439 [26] K. Valko, S. Nunhuck, C. Bevan, M.H. Abraham, D.P. Reynolds, Fast gradient HPLC
440 method to determine compounds binding to human serum albumin. Relationships with
441 octanol/water and immobilized artificial membrane lipophilicity., *J Pharm Sci*. 92 (2003)
442 2236–48. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jps.10494>.
- 443 [27] K. Valko, S. Rava, S. Bunally, S. Anderson, Revisiting the application of Immobilized
444 Artificial Membrane (IAM) chromatography to estimate in vivo distribution properties of
445 drug discovery compounds based on the model of marketed drugs., *ADMET DMPK*. 8
446 (2020) 78–97. <https://doi.org/10.5599/admet.757>.
- 447 [28] C. Stergiopoulos, F. Tsopeles, K. Valko, Prediction of hERG inhibition of drug
448 discovery compounds using biomimetic HPLC measurements., *ADMET DMPK*. 9 (2021)
449 191–207. <https://doi.org/10.5599/admet.995>.
- 450 [29] K.L. Valko, T. Zhang, Biomimetic properties and estimated in vivo distribution of
451 chloroquine and hydroxy-chloroquine enantiomers., *ADMET DMPK*. 9 (2021) 151–165.
452 <https://doi.org/10.5599/admet.929>.
- 453 [30] K. Ciura, S. Kovačević, M. Pastewska, H. Kapica, M. Kornela, W. Sawicki, Prediction of
454 the chromatographic hydrophobicity index with immobilized artificial membrane
455 chromatography using simple molecular descriptors and artificial neural networks, *J*
456 *Chromatogr A*. 1660 (2021) 462666. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2021.462666>.
- 457 [31] J. Fedorowicz, C.D. Cruz, M. Morawska, K. Ciura, S. Gilbert-Girard, L. Mazur, H.
458 Mäkkylä, P. Ilina, K. Savijoki, A. Fallarero, P. Tammela, J. Sączewski, Antibacterial and
459 antibiofilm activity of permanently ionized quaternary ammonium fluoroquinolones, *Eur J*
460 *Med Chem*. 254 (2023) 115373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2023.115373>.
- 461 [32] M. Pastewska, B. Żołnowska, S. Kovačević, H. Kapica, M. Gromelski, F. Stoliński, J.
462 Sławiński, W. Sawicki, K. Ciura, Modeling of Anticancer Sulfonamide Derivatives
463 Lipophilicity by Chemometric and Quantitative Structure-Retention Relationships
464 Approaches, *Molecules*. 27 (2022) 3965. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27133965>.
- 465 [33] S. Ulenberg, K. Ciura, P. Georgiev, M. Pastewska, G. Ślifirski, M. Król, F. Herold, T.
466 Bączek, Use of biomimetic chromatography and in vitro assay to develop predictive GA-

467 MLR model for use in drug-property prediction among anti-depressant drug candidates,
468 *Microchem J.* 175 (2022) 107183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2022.107183>.

469 [34] K. Ciura, J. Fedorowicz, P. Žuvela, M. Lovrić, H. Kapica, P. Baranowski, W. Sawicki,
470 M.W. Wong, J. Sączewski, Affinity of Antifungal Isoxazolo[3,4-b]pyridine-3(1H)-Ones to
471 Phospholipids in Immobilized Artificial Membrane (IAM) Chromatography, *Molecules.* 25
472 (2020) 4835. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25204835>.

473 [35] M. Pastewska, B. Bednarczyk-Cwynar, S. Kovačević, N. Buławska, S. Ulenberg, P.
474 Georgiev, H. Kapica, P. Kawczak, T. Bączek, W. Sawicki, K. Ciura, Multivariate assessment
475 of anticancer oleanane triterpenoids lipophilicity, *J Chromatogr A.* 1656 (2021) 462552.
476 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2021.462552>.

477 [36] K.L. Valko, S. Rava, S. Bunally, S. Anderson, Revisiting the application of Immobilized
478 Artificial Membrane (IAM) chromatography to estimate in vivo distribution properties of
479 drug discovery compounds based on the model of marketed drugs, *ADMET DMPK.* 0 (2020)
480 78–97. <https://doi.org/10.5599/admet.757>.

481 [37] M.D. Wilkinson, M. Dumontier, I.J. Aalbersberg, G. Appleton, M. Axton, A. Baak, N.
482 Blomberg, J.-W. Boiten, L.B. da S. Santos, P.E. Bourne, J. Bouwman, A.J. Brookes, T. Clark,
483 M. Crosas, I. Dillo, O. Dumon, S. Edmunds, C.T. Evelo, R. Finkers, A. Gonzalez-Beltran,
484 A.J.G. Gray, P. Groth, C. Goble, J.S. Grethe, J. Heringa, P.A.C. 't Hoen, R. Hooft, T. Kuhn,
485 R. Kok, J. Kok, S.J. Lusher, M.E. Martone, A. Mons, A.L. Packer, B. Persson, P. Rocca-
486 Serra, M. Roos, R. van Schaik, S.-A. Sansone, E. Schultes, T. Sengstag, T. Slater, G. Strawn,
487 M.A. Swertz, M. Thompson, J. van der Lei, E. van Mulligen, J. Velterop, A. Waagmeester, P.
488 Wittenburg, K. Wolstencroft, J. Zhao, B. Mons, The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific
489 data management and stewardship, 3 (2016) 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

490 [38] P. Gramatica, N. Chirico, E. Papa, S. Cassani, S. Kovarich, QSARINS: A new software
491 for the development, analysis, and validation of QSAR MLR models, *Journal of*
492 *Computational Chemistry.* 34 (2013) 2121–2132. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.23361>.

493 [39] Gajewicz, A., How to judge whether QSAR/read-across predictions can be trusted: a
494 novel approach for establishing a model's applicability domain, *Environ. Sci.: Nano.* 5 (2018)
495 408–421. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7en00774d>.

496 [40] H. Wickham, *ggplot2, Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*, (2016) 109–145.
497 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24277-4_6.

498 [41] K.L. Valko, S. Rava, S. Bunally, S. Anderson, Revisiting the application of Immobilized
499 Artificial Membrane (IAM) chromatography to estimate in vivo distribution properties of
500 drug discovery compounds based on the model of marketed drugs, *Admet Dmpk.* 0 (2020)
501 78–97. <https://doi.org/10.5599/admet.757>.

502 [42] A. Avdeef, K.J. Box, J.E.A. Comer, C. Hibbert, K.Y. Tam, pH-Metric logP 10.
503 Determination of Liposomal Membrane-Water Partition Coefficients of Ionizable Drugs,
504 *Pharm. Res.* 15 (1998) 209–215. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1011954332221>.

505 [43] D. Vrakas, C. Giaginis, A. Tsantili-Kakoulidou, Electrostatic interactions and ionization
506 effect in immobilized artificial membrane retention: A comparative study with octanol–water

507 partitioning, *Journal of Chromatography A*. 1187 (2008) 67–78.
508 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2008.01.079>.

509 [44] G. Russo, L. Grumetto, R. Szucs, F. Barbato, F. Lynen, Screening therapeutics according
510 to their uptake across the blood-brain barrier: A high throughput method based on
511 immobilized artificial membrane liquid chromatography-diode-array-detection coupled to
512 electrospray-time-of-flight mass spectrometry, *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 127 (2018) 72–84.
513 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2018.02.004>.

514 [45] G. Russo, L. Grumetto, R. Szucs, F. Barbato, F. Lynen, Determination of in Vitro and in
515 Silico Indexes for the Modeling of Blood–Brain Barrier Partitioning of Drugs via Micellar
516 and Immobilized Artificial Membrane Liquid Chromatography, *J. Med. Chem.* 60 (2017)
517 3739–3754. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.6b01811>.

518 [46] T.E. Yen, S. Agatonovic-Kustrin, A.M. Evans, R.L. Nation, J. Ryand, Prediction of drug
519 absorption based on immobilized artificial membrane (IAM) chromatography separation and
520 calculated molecular descriptors, *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*. 38
521 (2005) 472–478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2005.01.040>.

522 [47] F. Hollósy, K. Valkó, A. Hersey, S. Nunhuck, G. Kéri, C. Bevan, Estimation of Volume
523 of Distribution in Humans from High Throughput HPLC-Based Measurements of Human
524 Serum Albumin Binding and Immobilized Artificial Membrane Partitioning, *Journal of*
525 *Medicinal Chemistry*. 49 (2006) 6958–6971. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jm050957i>.

526 [48] A. Nasal, M. Sznitowska, A. Bucíński, R. Kaliszan, Hydrophobicity parameter from
527 high-performance liquid chromatography on an immobilized artificial membrane column and
528 its relationship to bioactivity, *Journal of Chromatography A*. 692 (1995) 83–89.
529 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9673\(94\)00689-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9673(94)00689-7).

530 [49] A.W. Sobańska, E. Brzezińska, IAM Chromatographic Models of Skin Permeation,
531 *Molecules*. 27 (2022) 1893. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27061893>.

532 [50] C. Stergiopoulos, F. Tsopeles, K. Valko, Prediction of hERG inhibition of drug
533 discovery compounds using biomimetic HPLC measurements, *Admet Dmpk*. 9 (2021) 191–
534 207. <https://doi.org/10.5599/admet.995>.

535 [51] M.A. Al-Haj, R. Kaliszan, A. Nasal, Test Analytes for Studies of the Molecular
536 Mechanism of Chromatographic Separations by Quantitative Structure–Retention
537 Relationships, *Anal. Chem.* 71 (1999) 2976–2985. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac9901586>.

538 [52] B. Buszewski, P. Žuvela, G. Sagandykova, J. Walczak-Skierska, P. Pomastowski, J.
539 David, M.W. Wong, Mechanistic Chromatographic Column Characterization for the Analysis
540 of Flavonoids Using Quantitative Structure-Retention Relationships Based on Density
541 Functional Theory, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 21 (2020) 2053. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21062053>.

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551 **Figures:**

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553 Figure 1. A) Distribution of chemical classes. C) Distribution of CHI_{IAM} among chemical
554 classes

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556 Figure 2. Results of exploratory analysis

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558 Figure 3) Results of KwLPR regression; A) Observed CHI_{IAM} vs. predicted by model; B)
559 RMSEP for tested groups of drug candidates; C) applicability domain defined using the
560 probability-oriented distance-based approach.

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562 **Tables:**

563 Table 1. Summary of previously published QSRR models dedicated to IAM-HPLC.

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565 Table 2. Compression of statical figures of obtained MLR and KwLPR models.

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Table 1. Summary of previously published QSRR models dedicated to IAM-HPLC.

Retention parameter, chromatographic condition, and type of analytes	Descriptors	chemometric tool	number of analytes	obtained statistical parameter	ref.
$\log k_w$ IAM.PC.C10/C3; water-acetonitrile mobile phase; heterogeneous group of molecules	LSER-Based Structural Descriptors of Abraham	MLR	58	$R = 0.988$	[51]
$\log k_{IAM}$ IAM.PC.DD2 50 mM ammonium acetate (pH 7.0) - acetonitrile mobile phase; heterogeneous group of molecules	LSER-Based Structural Descriptors of Abraham and net charge per molecule	MLR	53	$R^2 = 0.958$	[17]
$\log k_{IAM}$ IAM.PC.DD2 50 mM ammonium acetate (pH 7.0) - acetonitrile mobile phase; heterogeneous group of molecules	$ClogP$, rotatory bond (RotB), rings, molecular weight (MW) and total surface area (TSA)	PLS	55	$Q^2 = 0.902$ $RSME_P = 0.400$	[18]
$\log k_{IAM}$ IAM.PC.DD2 50 mM ammonium acetate (pH 7.0) - acetonitrile mobile phase; heterogeneous group of molecules	number of aromatic rings, mobility of π electrons, $ClogP$	LLR	55	$Q^2 = 0.9305$ $RMSE_P = 0.395$	[19]
$\log k_w$ IAM.PC.DD2 10 mM ammonium acetate (pH 6.5) – methanol; ionic liquids	$\log P$ and point charge	MLR	8	$R^2 = 0,99$ $s = 0.09$	[20]
$\log k_w$ IAM.PC.MG phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) - acetonitrile mobile phase; heterogeneous group of molecules	$milogP$, Heavy Atoms, mean of calculated hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB_M), rotatory bond	MLR	204	$R^2 = 0.81$ $Q^2 = 0.80$ $s = 0.438$	[21]
$\log k_w$ IAM.PC.DD2	$milogP$, Volume Diameter, hydrophilic-lipophilic balance corrected by polar surface area (HLB_{PSA}), rotatory bond	MLR	160	$R^2 = 0.85$ $Q^2 = 0.84$ $s = 0.459$	[21]

phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) - acetonitrile mobile phase; heterogeneous group of molecules					
$\log k_{IAM}$ IAM.PC.DD2 0.1% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) in water - acetonitrile mobile phases; flavonoids	minimum O-H bond strength, global hardness (η), HOMO-LUMO energy gap, natural bond orbital (NBO)	PLS	30	$RMSE = 1.60$	[52]
CHI_{IAM} IAM.PC.DD2 0.01 M Phosphate Buffer Saline (pH 7.4)	positively charged fraction (F^+), negatively charged fraction (F^-), $\log D_{pH 7.4}$,	MLR	56	$R = 0.938$, $S = 0.413$	[43]
CHI_{IAM} IAM.PC.DD2 Morpholinepropanesulfonic acid (pH 7.4)	positively charged fraction (F^+), negatively charged fraction (F^-), $\log D_{pH 7.4}$,	MLR	62	$R=0.948$, $s = 0.505$	[43]
CHI_{IAM} IAM.PC.DD2 phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) - acetonitrile mobile phase; oleanolic acid derivatives	Dragon descriptors	MLR	33	$R^2=0.947$ $Q^2=0.906$ $RMSE_{CV}=2.236$ $RMSE_P=2.171$	[35]
CHI_{IAM} IAM.PC.DD2 50 mM ammonium acetate (pH 7.4) - acetonitrile mobile phase; arylpiperazines derivatives	Dragon descriptors	MLR	25	$R^2=0.968$ $Q^2=0.942$ $RMSE_{CV}=0.042$ $RMSE_P=0.058$	[33]
$\log K_{IAM}$ IAM.PC.DD2 50 mM ammonium acetate (pH 7.4) - acetonitrile mobile phase; sulfonamides derivatives	Dragon descriptors	MLR	27	$CCC = 0.884$ $RMSE_P = 0.173$	[32]
CHI_{IAM} IAM.PC.DD2 phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) - acetonitrile mobile phase; isoxazolone derivatives,	Dragon descriptors	PLS	26	$Q^2 = 0.933$ $RMSE_P = 1.983$	[34]
CHI_{IAM} IAM.PC.DD2	$\log D_{pH 7.4}$, numbers of H-donors, polar surface area (PSA), molecular volume	ANN	261	$CCC = 0.822$ $RMSE_P = 8.2$	[30]

50 mM ammonium acetate (pH 7.4) - acetonitrile mobile phase; heterogeneous group of molecules					
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MLR - multivariable linear regression, PLS - Partial least squares regression, LLR - local lazy regression, ANN - artificial neural network, s - standard error of estimates

Table 2. Comparison of statistical figures of obtained MLR and KwLPR models.

Model	R^2	RMSE _c	Q^2_{loo}	RMSE _{loo}	Q^2	CCC	RMSE _p
MLR	0.742	8.911	0.736	9.017	0.701	0.770	11.689
KwLPR	0.866	6.435	0.782	8.184	0.812	0.884	6.739